

THE APPRAISAL OF BIAS AND POWER AS EXPRESSED IN SEVERAL INDONESIAN NEWS ARTICLES ABOUT INDONESIA NEW HOUSE SPEAKER INAUGURATION

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Abstract

This research discusses about bias and power in the four chosen news articles published by the Jakarta Post. Those four articles discuss the competition between two bickering factions inside Golkar Party, Bakrie's group and Laksono's group, to grab the position of new house speaker in early 2016. The main goal of this research is to reveal the power and bias applied implicitly through the linguistic features enacted in media. The revelation of bias is analyzed through its linguistic choice by using Appraisal theory proposed by Martin and White (2005). Since bias is one of the social inequalities phenomena, this research is revealed under Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) scope, especially using Fircloough's three dimensional frameworks, which deals with analyzing the relation between language and social context. The Jakarta Post needs to obey the principles of journalist that are being neutral, independent and objective in informing the news. However, the result of this research shows that the media is possible to do bias because of political interest.

Keywords: Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA), New House Speaker Inauguration, Bias, Appraisal theory

1. Introduction

News article is the media which provides the daily information for the reader. Since the technological term is developed, the news daily can be consumed via online. Whatever its form, media is still interrelated with the language because the content of the media includes language as the communication instrument to make meaning (O'Keffee, cited in Simpson, 2011:67). Making meaning here means that media can inform the world event based on their point of view. Since the media has a role to decide the point of view of the fact solely, it leads the media to possibly stand upon one side of the event informed. The one-sidedness of the media in informing the issue is called media bias.

Actually, the media has the principle and ethical code to be neutral in informing the information. Yet, as the institution, the media producer tends to do bias because of certain interests. The stronger interests are caused of political and economical interest. The political interest, then, drives the media to support one of the groups intentionally and it leads the reader, as the consumer, to follow with the issue informed in the media. The media also consider the political interest because of supporting certain elite group such as political party or certain group in the government.

The one of the political events in Indonesia is the internal dispute inside the big party in Indonesia namely *Golongan Karya* (Golkar). It becomes the controversial issue as it involves several well-known political figures in the government. All of Indonesian

media have reported this issue. One of the media that informs this issue is *the Jakarta Post*. The internal conflict inside the Golkar Party is about two dispute camps within the Golkar party which want to nominate their members as the new house speaker to replace Setya Novanto, the former of house speaker. They are Aburizal Bakrie's camp and Agung Laksono's camp.

From those social issues about two bickering factions, it becomes the social context in this research. The main concern of this research is the bias of the media, *the Jakarta Post*, upon the one faction inside Golkar Party that is informed in the four chosen news articles. Since there are two bickering factions inside Golkar party which want to grab the successor of new house speaker, *the Jakarta Post* has released the information that contain of certain tendency upon one particular faction, especially from Aburizal Bakrie's faction. The bias, then, is revealed through the linguistic features enacted in the news articles.

The revelation of bias is conducted under three methods that consist of Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA), Appraisal System proposed by Martin and White (2005) and the notion of bias.

As explained before, media is interrelated with linguistic features. Regarding to the linguistic features, the Appraisal is the applicable tools to analyze the linguistic features. It deals with the evaluation using three sub-systems. They are Attitude, Engagement and Graduation. Attitude deals with evaluating something emotively. Engagement deals with adding the external voice and modality as the rhetorical proposition in the

statement. Meanwhile graduation concerns to the amplifying and minimizing the sense of the statement.

Additionally, this research is also conducted under CDA because it reveals the power abuse and social inequality led by the media through the linguistic features enacted by the journalist solely in media. As the CDA analyst, the assumption of bias done by the media is applied and I believe that the media oppose one certain faction from Agung Laksono's group.

Related to the problem to analyze, then, the research questions are emerged to get the clear path in analyzing the problem in this research. The research questions are:

- a. How does the appraisal work on the four *the Jakarta Post* news articles?
- b. How does the news articles *the Jakarta Post* take a position upon the dispute issue inside Golkar Party?

2. Research Methodology

This research uses qualitative reaserch since this research applies the interpretation and description, mainly to interpret and describe the word, language and clauses in the news articles. As Denzin and Lincoln states in Marlengen that the process of interpretation is covered in qualitative types (2014:23). It means that, the result which employs a descriptive method is included into the qualitative research.

In addition, the object of the research is taken from the online daily news. Since the online daily news is also compatible and efficient instrument of the documentary source, the case of documentary not always archived in the form of paper. As MacCulloh cited in Marlengen that the data collected from documentary sources can be from government paper, diaries, newspaper and so on (2014: 23). Thus, the strategy of documentary fits in this research.

As mentioned above, the object of this research is news articles namely *the Jakarta Post*. The news articles are provided in online and printed. Meanwhile, in this research, the articles are gathered from the internet. They are accessed from www.thejakartapost.com website page. There are four news articles gathered as the object of research which discuss about the competition between two dispute camps in the Golkar Party to grab the house speaker position. The news articles were accessed on January 28th, 2016.

The next is processing the data. Firstly the data are sorted based on the bias-contained in the news articles. The next step is categorizing the linguistic features distributed in each sentence selected. It is categorized

using three resources of appraisal proposed by Martin and White (2005) such as attitude, engagement and graduation. Then, labeling the word served bias and power using those three resources of appraisal. Those three appraisal sub systems will be categorized in this way: Attitude which consists of affect, judgment and appreciation is labeled on the quality expressed in adjective and adverb, process expressed in verb and comment expressed in modal adjunct. Engagement which consists of proclaim, disclaim, attribution and entertain is labeled on the verb and modality. Then, graduation which consists of focus and force is labeled in the intensity of the evaluative word. The last step is interpreting the data to make the plain explanation of bias in the text.

Regarding to the CDA scope used in this analysis, the three-dimensional framework of discourse proposed by Fairclough (1989) is employed. The method deals with three analyses. Firstly is called Micro analysis which deals with describing the linguistic features in the news articles. Mezzo analysis becomes the second method that deals with interpreting the data by looking closer to the discourse practice and its relation with linguistic choice the media. Lastly, macro analysis deals with explaining the conclusion of the relation between discursive practices in the media with the social practice in the reality.

This research is

3. Result

This research provides the results from the three sub-systems of Appraisal. Firstly, the result of linguistic features distributed in the media is analyzed with Attitude system. The result is shown as follow:

The Results of Attitude Analysis

Attitude's sources	st 1 articl e	nd 2 articl e	rd 3 articl e	th 4 articl e	Tota l
Affect	-	-	-	-	4
Judgment	2	6	1	1	10
Appreciatio n	3	4	1	6	14
Overall	3	10	2	7	24

The most dominant of attitude analysis is appreciation. The most use of appreciation is applied in the second news articles.

The next is the result of Engagement system applied to sort the linguistic features. The result is shown as follow:

The Results of Engagement Analysis

Engagement's sources	st 1 artic le	nd 2 artic le	rd 3 artic le	th 4 artic le	Tot al
Deny	1	1	3	1	6
Counter	1	3	-	-	6
Affirm	-	2	-	-	2
Concede	-	-	-	-	-
Pronounce	-	-	-	-	-
Endorse	-	-	2	-	2
Entertain	2	-	1	2	5
Acknowledgm ent	4	6	3	3	16
Distance	-	-	-	-	-
Overall	8	12	9	6	37

The most dominant of the Engagement system is heteroglossia especially acknowledgment. It is followed by counter and deny in the same total and then entertain as the next domination after both of them.

Lastly is the use of Graduation. Actually, the use of graduation is independent with modality in entertain as well as in the appreciation. It aims to emphasize the statement with showing the intensity of probability and certainty also positive and negative of the appreciation. The rest of the graduation term is used to show the adverbial of time. The result is shown as follow:

The Results of Graduation Analysis

Source of Graduation	st 1 artic le	nd 2 artic le	rd 3 artic le	th 4 artic le	Tota l
Intensificati on					
Low	1	-	-	-	1
Median	2	-	-	1	3
High	1	1	-	-	2
Quantificati on					
Low	-	-	-	-	-
Median	-	-	-	-	-
High	1	5	-	1	7
Soften					
Low	-	-	-	-	-
Median	-	-	-	-	-
High	-	-	-	-	-
Sharpen					
Low	-	-	-	-	-
Median	-	-	-	-	-
High	-	-	-	-	-

Overall	5	6	-	2	13
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The result of Graduation system is mostly equal between intensification and quantification. However, the media prefer employs force as the graduation system rather than focus.

4. Discussion

From the result before shows that the most dominant use of Appraisal, the first news article is dominantly used acknowledgement in each news articles. It assigns that *the Jakarta Post* provides the politicians' quotation to show that its news is included in the hard news. Hard news provides the opinion from the informant in order to represent the point of view of the journalist itself. In addition, the media also uses the other sources to emphasize the evaluation upon two bickering factions. The sources used after in the four news articles are different each other.

The first news article supplies the entertain as the second domination of Appraisal system. It is supplied for both existences of Laksono's group and Bakrie's group. The high scale of entertain is directed to government and Bakrie's group.

The second news articles, then, mostly employs positive judgment in which it is directed to government's capacity to revoke Laksono's group. The following source is the use of counter to maintain the solidarity upon government and Bakrie's group.

The use of denial becomes the second dominating system in the third news article. It is directed to the Laksono's authority. It assigns that the capacity of Laksono is rejected. Additionally, this news article is seemingly neutral with providing two opinions from two bickering factions. However, the strong argument is asserted for Bakrie's group.

Lastly, the fourth news article uses positive appreciation directed to Ade Komarudin's inauguration, member of Bakrie's group. The endorsement is employed in this news article as the support of the media upon Ade's nomination.

The result of the analysis above shows that *the Jakarta Post* tends to gain support and bias upon Aburizal Bakrie's group as well as maintain the solidarity to the government too through the linguistic features enacted by media. It includes in the discourse practice created by media.

As the CDA analyst, we need to know the producer of the media in order to reveal the relation and reason of why the producer creates such discourse practice in the media itself. *The Jakarta Post* is established by four collaborations of four media. Then, the founder is Ali Murtopo, the ministry of information as well as member of Golkar Party in the new order regime. Thus, this media tends to support Golkar party as the successor of new house speaker.

Although the strong support is dedicated for Golkar party, still, the media keeps the solidarity either upon the governmental line. The reason is because media is still founded under politician and governmental line. In addition, the media of *the Jakarta Post* still submits under government's authority, especially under Jokowi's parlement. *The Jakarta Post's* head of editorial staff, Meidyatama Suryodiningrat, was ever accepting the offer from Owned-State Enterprise (BUMN) ministry as the new director for Antara news to replace Siful Hadi under the Jokowi's leadership (Hardiyana, 2016). So that is why, the media still maintains a solidarity upon governmental line.

After knowing that *the Jakarta Post* tries to gain the support for Bakrie's group and maintain solidarity upon the government, the reason of why the media bias upon those two groups is necessary to reveal. The reason is because the media want to maintain their political power or political interest, especially symbiosis mutualism relationship between government and Golkar party, since Golkar party can influence the government making the rule in the parliament. *The Jakarta Post* is also pro to the governmental line.

Political interest affects the media to not doing neutrality in informing the information. Actually, it abuses the journalistic principles such as objectivity, fairness, balance and neutrality in informing the information. The balance information should be the standard of the media in informing the fact because we live in a democracy country as our culture and ideology in which the justice is highly respected. Therefore, the media still needs to use the principle of journalistic even the balance is never perfectly attained. But, at least, the media needs to inform the information even in the nearly balance.

Based on the analysis, the humor on the selected data

5. Conclusion

After all the result and discussion has been drawn before, the vivid conclusion is presented in this part in order to answer the research questions presented in the previous part.

Dealing with first question, the appraisal is worked through the distribution of linguistic features in the four chosen news articles as the choice of the media to appraise and evaluate the event informed. The distribution, then, is labeled with three sub-systems of Appraisal. The attitude is distributed in the adverbial, adjectival or phrases that are expressed in negative or positive way. It uses to express the attitude of the media upon the issue. Then, the engagement is realized into the proposition by the external voice, rhetorical statement and modality. It construes the dialogical interaction provided by the authorial voice and external voice for the reader to receive the

statement whether it is authoritative or open to discuss. It also construes the probability or certainty of the statement through the feature of modality. Lastly, the graduation deals with up-scaling and down-scaling the sense of the statement.

As the result, the most dominant of the Appraisal system is acknowledgment, as part of heteroglossia. It assigns that, the media employs informants' opinion in order to share the same point of view with the opinion.

The second dominating system is positive appreciation, as the system of attitude. It assigns that the media appreciates the one faction, especially Bakrie's group, who is supported by the media in the positive way. It emphasizes that the media is on behalf upon one particular faction.

The third dominating system is counter. Counter deals with providing two contradictory propositions with the preposition as the connector. The first proposition contains of confessing the government authority and power. On the contrary, the second proposition, the statement mostly contains of blaming the government for not installing Bakrie as the continue effort implicitly. However, the media is still gaining the solidarity upon government with confessing the authority of the government.

Additionally, the reason of media support Bakrie's group and gain the solidarity to the government is because political interest. Still, the bias done by the media is not neutral because it can gain the different effect for the reader's interpretation from the real event and true culture in the social practice. The balance of the information should be the standard of the media in informing the fact because we live in a democracy country as our culture and ideology in which the justice is highly respected. However, the neutrality as the symbol of fairness in informing the information in media is not really considered because of political or certain interest by the producer. However, as the media, even the perfectionist of neutrality cannot be reached, at least the approximate to reach balance information is need. It is because the journalistic principal consists of objectivities, fairness, balance and neutrality.

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